

Study of the impact of slope morphometric characteristics on soil erosion: a case study of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17826548>

Ulviyya N. Isgandarova

PhD, Senior Lecturer

Nakhchivan State University, Azerbaijan

E-mail: uisgenderova86@gmail.com

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9875-1176>

Turkana A. Aliyeva

PhD, Lecturer

Nakhchivan State University, Azerbaijan

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2595-6669>

E-mail: turkanaaliyeva044@gmail.com

Mahammad B. Guliyev

PhD student, Lecturer

Nakhchivan State University, Azerbaijan

E-mail: m.guliyev.ordubad92@gmail.com

<https://orcid.org/0009-0004-3858-1004>

Abstract: The article investigates the impact of the morphometric characteristics of slopes on soil erosion in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. In the Autonomous Republic, where the amount of arable land per capita is low, studying the morphometric indicators of slopes is of great importance to arrange the efficient use of soils. The continental climate of the area leads to poor vegetation development, which in turn increases the erosion risk of slopes. During the research, Geographic Information Systems (GIS) technologies, field research materials, Landsat Satellite Images, Google Earth Pro, and ArcGIS 10.3 software were used and maps reflecting the morphometric indicators of the Autonomous Republic's territory were created. The areas with different slope gradients were calculated and the erosion risk was determined. Mapping and analyzing erosion-prone areas play an important role in the development of sustainable land-use strategies.

Key words: *Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, erosion, slope steepness, slope orientation, relief*

Introduction

The Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, located between the Daralayaz and Zangezur Mountain Ranges and the Araz River, covers an area of 550,275 hectares. As a region with the limited arable land per capita ensuring the maximum efficient use of land resources in the Autonomous Republic is a pressing issue. The scarcity of fertile soils contributes to potential food shortages (Guliyeva, 2011, p.182). Therefore, the efficient use and protection of soil cover are essential to achieve sustainable agricultural development.

Soil erosion is a major ecogeographical problem that leads to the degradation of soil quality, decreased agricultural productivity and landscape degradation (Iskenderova, 2022, pp. 66–69). Morphometric factors—such as slope gradient, aspect, length and shape—play a significant role in the development of erosion processes. Weak vegetation cover further intensifies erosion, resulting in soil degradation (Isgandarova, 2024, p.152). Thus, determining slope gradient and aspect is of crucial importance. This study investigates the impact of slope morphometric parameters on soil erosion in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic using GIS- and DEM-based methods.

Materials and Methods. The main materials for the study included field observations conducted on various slopes within the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, topographic and soil maps, as well as, relevant satellite images. The slopes selected for analysis were primarily

located in the mid and high-mountain areas of the Shahbuz, Ordubad and Julfa districts. The morphometric characteristics of the terrain (slope gradient, slope length, aspect, and shape) were analyzed based on digital elevation models (DEM) using ArcGIS software.

It is well known that in different periods, slope gradients have been measured using various methods and tools. In accordance with modern requirements, the determination of slope gradients was carried out by using Geographic Information Systems (GIS) technologies, field research materials, Landsat Satellite Images, Google Earth Pro and ArcGIS 10.3 software. As a result, a slope gradient map of the Autonomous Republic was produced and diagrams illustrating the spatial distribution of slope gradients across the area were compiled.

Analysis and Discussion. When soil is used under a monoculture system for many years, it becomes depleted: certain microelements are exhausted while others accumulate in excess. Since a large portion of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic consists of mountainous and foothill areas, erosion processes are widespread, affecting up to 70% of the territory (Hajiyev, 2010). Water and wind erosion are the predominant forms observed, with water erosion being the most dominant type in the region (Hajiyev, 2004). In areas affected by water erosion, soils lose their natural fertility, because along with the washed-away particles, humus, nutrients, applied organic and mineral fertilizers from the plow layer are also removed, leading to the deterioration of soil structure. Consequently, these soils are gradually excluded from agricultural circulation.

The occurrence and development of erosion processes under any environmental condition primarily depend on relief features, particularly the slope gradient, aspect, and surface configuration of the slope (i.e., the alternation frequency of rough, concave, and convex forms). The slope gradient is one of the most critical factors determining the potential erosion hazard (Mustafayev, 1974). In foothill and mountainous regions, where agricultural activities are carried out on slopes of varying gradients and aspects, the creation of surface slope maps for areas prone to heavy rainfall is essential. Using modern methods, a slope gradient map of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic was prepared (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Map of steepness of slopes of Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic

The influence of slope gradient on soil erosion in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic is highly significant, as the region's relief mainly consists of mountainous and foothill landscapes (Babayev, 1999, p.298). This makes slope steepness one of the key factors directly affecting erosion intensity. Steeper slopes increase erosion risk, as rainfall and irrigation water move faster along inclined surfaces, carrying soil particles away (Shukuri, 2005, p.496). In the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, erosion processes are particularly active on slopes steeper than 8°, where both rill and surface erosion are widespread.

Analysis of the prepared maps and table indicates that 27% of the total area of the Autonomous Republic—approximately 1,497 km² (149,675 ha)—has a slope of 0–5°, 21% or 1,172 km² (117,209 ha) has a slope of 5–10°, 26% or 1,442 km² (144,172 ha) has a slope of 10–20°, 16% or 864 km² (86,393 ha) has a slope of 20–30°, and 10% or 528 km² (52,826 ha) consists of areas with slopes greater than 30°. These data are summarized in the following table.

Table 1. Area of territories with different inclinations

Area	Steepness				
	≤5	5-10	10-20	20-30	≥30
Hectares	149675	117209	144172	86393	52826
Sq.km	1497	1172	1442	864	528
Percentage	27	21	26	16	10

Mathematical and statistical calculations based on the map analysis revealed that 2,669 km² (266,884 ha) of the land with slopes up to 10°, which is intensively used for agriculture, corresponds to plains and foothill areas up to 1,200 meters above the sea level. Within this territory, 2,756 ha are perennial crops, 8,605 ha are meadow-swamp soils, 40,974 ha are cultivated lands, 403 ha are forested areas, 66,265 ha are pastures, 5,712 ha are saline lands, and 14,192 ha are settlements—amounting to a total of 1,389 km². Approximately 1,000 km² of the land with slopes up to 10° are used as village pastures and rangelands, while the remaining part includes transport networks, water bodies and other areas affected by natural and anthropogenic degradation.

The degree of slope inclination also varies across districts. Slopes of up to 10° are most common in Sadarak, Sharur, Kangarli and Babek districts, while the territories of Ordubad, Shahbuz and Julfa districts exhibit steeper slopes. In the high-mountain areas of Ordubad, Shahbuz and Julfa districts, slopes exceed 15° and erosion proceeds more rapidly in the areas with sparse vegetation cover. In the foothill zones of Babek, Kangarli and Sadarak districts, slopes between 5° and 15°—particularly those under the cultivation and poorly managed irrigation—are highly susceptible to erosion.

The study shows that determining slope gradients is essential for assessing areas at risk of erosion and preventing nutrient loss in soils. According to studies by Kh.M. Mustafayev, on a vegetation-free slope with a 7° gradient, 140 tons of soil are washed away per hectare, whereas on a 15° slope, soil loss reaches 280 tons per hectare (Mustafayev, 1974). Thus, a two-fold increase in slope gradient approximately doubles the intensity of erosion.

The orientation of the slopes also significantly impacts soil erosion, as it directly affects soil moisture, solar radiation, evaporation, humidity balance, vegetation development and surface runoff. Determining slope aspect is scientifically important to study the distribution of soil types and vegetation cover. The amount of precipitation and moisture varies depending on slope orientation. South-facing slopes receive higher solar radiation, resulting in greater evaporation and weaker vegetation growth. Dense vegetation cover helps prevent soil erosion on slopes. In contrast, north-facing slopes, which receive less sunlight and retain higher soil moisture, support better vegetation development. The weak vegetation on south-facing slopes accelerates degradation. Therefore, when studying factors contributing to soil degradation, it is necessary to determine the spatial distribution of slope orientation. For this purpose, a map of

slope orientations for different parts in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic was prepared (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Slope orientation map of Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic

Based on the analysis of the prepared maps and field studies, it was determined that north-facing slopes of the autonomous republic cover an area of 1,007 km², characterized by lower temperatures and higher humidity compared to other slopes. Flat surfaces, which cover 85 km², display nearly uniform distribution of precipitation, temperature, and solar radiation; hence, they possess similar soil and vegetation types. In mountainous areas, the variation in slope orientation has led to a diversity of soil and vegetation cover. GIS analyses conducted in the mountainous districts of the Autonomous Republic show that erosion processes are more intensive on south-facing slopes, while soils on north and east-facing slopes are relatively more stable. In contrast, in arid zones with west-facing slopes, wind erosion is also observed.

Conclusion

The research findings have shown that the morphometric characteristics of slopes have a direct impact on the intensity of soil erosion. In areas with a high risk of erosion, a number of measures must be implemented to prevent soil degradation. To achieve this:

- Trees and shrubs with fibrous root systems should be planted on slopes;
- Terraces should be constructed on steep slopes to reduce water runoff velocity and ensure soil stability;
- Intensive irrigation methods should be replaced with drip or sprinkler irrigation systems;
- Grazing activities should be controlled;

Awareness campaigns should be conducted among local population and farmers regarding soil erosion control measures.

These actions contribute to both the conservation of soil resources and the sustainable development of agriculture.

Mapping and analyzing erosion-prone areas play a crucial role in developing sustainable land-use strategies. Identifying erosion-risk zones in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic enables the effective planning of soil conservation measures.

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